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(CRIHS-2K19)

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Goa State Branch, Goa

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TABLE OF CONTENT FOR SELECTED ABSTRACTS

ABSTRACT CODE	CORRESPONDING AUTHER	TITLE OF ABSTRACT	PAGE NO.
PHARMACEUTICS – (CRIHS-O-CEU)			
CRIHS-O-CEU-001	G. Ganesh	DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM RISEDRONATE	S-1
CRIHS-O-CEU-002	Gummuluri Sriram	BUPRENORPHINE-BUCCAL TABLETS	S-2
CRIHS-O-CEU-003	N. Naveen Reddy	TAMOXIFEN CITRATE - ORAL DISPERSIBLE TABLETS	S-3
CRIHS-O-CEU-004	Shilpa Bhilegaonkar	COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY OF “ROLL-ON” FORMULATION WITH VARYING METHODS OF DRUG LOADING IN TREATMENT OF ONYCHOMICOSIS	S-4
CRIHS-O-CEU-005	Shaik Harun Rasheed	FORMULATION AND IN-VITRO EVALUATION OF BILAYERED FLOATING TABLETS OF CANDESARTAN USING VARIOUS POLYMERS	S-5
CRIHS-O-CEU-006	Madhu Burra	ENHANCED INTESTINAL ABSORPTION AND BIOAVAILABILITY OF RALOXIFENE HYDROCHLORIDE VIA LYOPHILIZED SOLID LIPID NANOPARTICLES	S-6
CRIHS-O-CEU-007	MD. Yasmeen	DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MOUTH DISSOLVING TABLETS OF ZOLMITRIPTAN USING NOVEL SUPER DISINTEGRANTS	S-7
CRIHS-O-CEU-008	B. Sai Krishnam Raju	DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MODIFIED RELEASE SOLID ORAL DOSAGE FORM (ENTACAPONE)	S-8
CRIHS-O-CEU-009	G. Srujana	DESIGN AND CHARACTERISATION OF RIFAMIXIMIN MULTIPARTICULATE COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY	S-9
CRIHS-O-CEU-010	B. Raja Narender	FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ANTICANCER DRUG (TAMOXIFEN) LOADED NANOSPONGES	S-10
CRIHS-O-CEU-011	T. Pandu Raju	FORMULATION AND IN VITRO EVALUATION OF FILMS FOR BUCCAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM (OMEPRAZOLE)	S-11
CRIHS-O-CEU-012	Vanga Sridhar	FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL DOSAGE FORM EXHIBITING ANTI-ACNE ACTIVITY	S-12
PHARMACEUTICAL CHEMISTRY – (CRIHS-O-CHEM)			
CRIHS-O-CHEM-001	Lingaiah Nagarapu	POTENTIAL ANTI-PROLIFERATIVE AGENTS FROM 2,3-DIMETHYL BENZOCYCLOHEPTENONES-PART 4	S-13
CRIHS-O-CHEM-002	V. Lakshmi Aparna	STUDY ON ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY METHODS OF CITRUS SPECIES	S-14
CRIHS-O-CHEM-003	Anjali Bakshi	STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANIOUS ESTIMATION OF IVACAFTOR AND TEZACAFTOR IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM	S-15
CRIHS-O-CHEM-004	Celina Nazareth	UV SPECTROSCOPIC ESTIMATION OF EZETIMIBE AND ROSUVASTATIN	S-16
CRIHS-O-CHEM-005	Rasapelly Ramesh Kumar	DARIVATIZATION AND PHARMACOLOGICAL EVALUTION NEW 4-SUBSTITUTED 5-PHENYL-3-MERCAPTO 1,2,4-TRIAZOLE	S-17
CRIHS-O-CHEM-006	Swetha Sri R	A STABILITY INDICATING ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS QUANTIFIATION OF ARTEMETHER AND LUMEFANTRINE IN COMBINED DOSAGE FORMS BY RP-HPLC	S-18
CRIHS-O-CHEM-007	Venugopal Muralidharan	DESIGN, SYNTHESIS, ANTICANCER EVALUATION AND DOCKING STUDIES OF NOVEL PYRAZOLINE DERIVATIVES OBTAINED VIA REACTIONS INVOLVING CHALCONES	S-19
CRIHS-O-CHEM-008	S. Ushasree	REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID	S-20

		CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF PANTOPRAZOLE IN PURE AND ITS DOSAGE FORMS	
CRIHS-O-CHEM-009	G. Sandhya	DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF LEVOFLOXACIN AND AMBROXOL HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM	S-21
CRIHS-O-CHEM-010	B. Raj Kumar	REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF RABEPRAZOLE IN PURE AND ITS DOSAGE FORM	S-22
PHARMACOGNOSY – (CRIHS - COG)			
CRIHS-O-COG-001	Deepthi Yada	REVIEW ON HYPTIS SUAVEOLENS (L.) POIT (LAMIACEAE) - A POTENTIAL PLANT	S-23
CRIHS-O-COG-002	Divya Yada	PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF <i>TRIANTHEMA PORTULACASTRUM</i> LINN.	S-24
CRIHS-O-COG-003	Divya Yada	TRIANTHEMA PORTULACASTRUM LINN. AND ITS UTILITY - A REVIEW	S-25
CRIHS-O-COG-004	P. Mamatha	BIOTRANSFORMATION OF FRUIT LITTER IN TO VANILLIN BY FUNGI	S-26
PHARMACOLOGY – (CRIHS - COL)			
CRIHS-O-COL-001	P. Pandian	INVITRO ANTI-INFLAMMATORY SCREENING OF MARINE ALGAE SPECIES <i>SARGASSUM TENERRIMUM</i>	S-27
CRIHS-O-COL-002	Chandrika D	ESTIMATION OF PREVALANCE ON SELF MEDICATION AMONG PHARMACY STUDENTS	S-28
CRIHS-O-COL-003	Chandrika D	SAFETY AND EFFICACY OF UNDENATURED TYPE II COLLAGEN IN THE TREATMENT OF OSTEOARTHRITIS OF THE KNEE	S-29
CRIHS-O-COL-004	T.V.D. Vinoothna	RETROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DRUG UTILISATION OF PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS Vs H ₂ RECEPTORS BLOCKERS	S-30
CRIHS-O-COL-005	V. Satya Chakravarthy	EFFECTIVENESS OF VIRTUAL REALITY BASED THERAPY IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY – A REVIEW	S-31
CRIHS-O-COL-006	D. Rama Krishna Prasad	THE EVOLUTION OF TREATMENT OF MAJOR DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS FROM PSYCHOSURGERY TO NEUROIMAGING AND NEUROMODULATION	S-32
CRIHS-O-COL-007	D. Neelima Chowdary	THE EVOLUTION OF NEUROMODULATION SURGERY FOR PSYCHIATRIC DISORDERS	S-33
CRIHS-O-COL-008	U.N.S.V. Sugatri	EVALUATION OF PATIENT ADHERENCE TO TB TREATMENT AND ROLE OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST IN IMPROVING PATIENT ADHERENCE	S-34
CRIHS-O-COL-009	Dr. Darabadi Rispa	ECONOMIC BURDEN AND REASONS FOR DELAY IN FIRST PSYCHIATRIC CONSULTATION - AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY	S-35
CRIHS-O-COL-010	T. Akhila	OUTCOMES OF LIVING RELATED KIDNEY TRANSPLANT RECIPIENT WITH TRIPLE IMMUNOSUPPRESSANTS (TACROLIMUS, MYCOPHENOLATE, STEROIDS) AT 6 MONTHS POST TRANSPLANTATION	S-36
CRIHS-O-COL-011	P.V.S.N. Vimala	SAFETY AND EFFICACY IN CURRENT MANAGEMENT OF TRACHOMA	S-37
CRIHS-O-COL-012	G. Sumalatha	DECEASED DONOR KIDNEY TRANSPLANT WITH ATG INDUCTION AND TRIPLE IMMUNOSUPPRESSIVE AGENTS (TACROLIMUS, MMF, PREDNISOLONE)	S-38

CRIHS-O-COL-013	M.V.S.L. Priyanka	COMPARISON OF DRUG THERAPY AND INTERVENTIONAL THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH UNCOMPLICATED HEART ATTACK	S-39
CRIHS-O-COL-014	K. Dulcie Moses	PARACETAMOL SENSITIVITY AND TREATMENT APPROACH – A CASE REPORT	S-40
CRIHS-O-COL-015	Anju Sharma	ASSESSMENT OF APPROPRIATENESS OF ANTIBIOTIC PRESCRIPTIONS IN SURGICAL PROPHYLAXIS OF ORTHOPEDIC PROCEDURES	S-41
CRIHS-O-COL-016	Dr. G. Chiranjeevi	EVALUATION OF ANTIDEPRESSANT ACTIVITY OF HYPERICUM PERFORATUM USING EXPERIMENTAL MODELS OF DEPRESSION IN RATS	S-42
CRIHS-O-COL-017	Dr. Hareesh Dara	EVALUATION AND COMPARISON OF REGULATORY STRATEGY AND COMMUNICATIONS RECEIVED FROM VARIOUS REGULATORY AUTHORITIES DURING PRE & POST REGISTRATION OF "PIPERACILLIN AND TAZOBACTAM FOR INJECTION"	S-43
CRIHS-O-COL-018	P. Aswini	INVESTIGATIONAL STUDIES ON CARCINOMA IN MALE RATS	S-44
CRIHS-O-COL-019	P. Manju	ACECLOFENAC-INDUCED PHYSICOCHEMICAL ALTERATIONS IN TOXICITY AMONG MALE ALBINO RATS	S-45
CRIHS-O-COL-020	M. Mounika	STUDY OF ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS ASSOCIATED WITH CHEMOTHERAPY OF BREAST CANCER	S-46
CRIHS-O-COL-021	Y. Sreehari Bharadwaj	DRUG UTILIZATION PATTERN OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE PATIENT UNDERGOING HAEMODIALYSIS	S-47
CRIHS-O-COL-022	B. Kiranmai	ROLE OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST TO IMPROVE THE ADHERENCE OF CONTRACEPTION	S-48
CRIHS-O-COL-023	K. Maneesha	CANCER THERAPY-RELATED CARDIAC DYSFUNCTION AND HEART FAILURE	S-49
CRIHS-O-COL-024	Pavan	BREAST CANCER: THERAPEUTIC APPROACHES AND CHARACTERISTIC OBSERVATIONAL STUDY IN PATIENTS	S-50
CRIHS-O-COL-025	B. Prashanth Naidu	EVALUATION OF RATIONAL USE OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR SURGICAL PROPHYLAXIS	S-51
CRIHS-O-COL-026	V. Sumanth Roy	OBSERVATIONAL STUDY TO MEASURE ANTI-EPILEPTIC DRUG ADHERENCE	S-52
CRIHS-O-COL-027	V. Shivani	A STUDY OF MEDICATION ERRORS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL	S-53
CRIHS-O-COL-028	Sowjanya I	CASE STUDY ON LYME DISEASE	S-54
CRIHS-O-COL-029	V. Ushasree	ADVANCES IN GENE THERAPY AND THE ROLE OF PHARMACIST IN GENE THERAPY	S-55
CRIHS-O-COL-030	Anusha Patil	IMPACT OF PATIENT COUNSELLING ON HTN	S-56
CRIHS-O-COL-031	Ch. Raju	CASE PRESENTATION ON CONGENITAL CYANOTIC HEART DISEASE	S-57
CRIHS-O-COL-032	MD. Mansoor Ali	PHARMACOEPIDEMIOLOGICAL STUDY ON CEREBROVASCULAR	S-58
GENERAL PHARMA – (CRIHS - GEN)			
CRIHS-O-GEN-001	Kiransha R.	ASSESSMENT OF SENSORIMOTOR DYSFUNCTION OF THE WRIST: A SCOPING REVIEW	S-59
MEDICAL – (CRIHS - MED)			
CRIHS-O-MED-001	Dr. Kavita Nathan	A STUDY AND REVIEW OF TOPICAL CORTICOSTEROID ABUSE IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL	S-60
CRIHS-O-MED-002	Dr. Y. Shiva Krishna	AN OVERVIEW AND ASSESSMENT OF MATERIOVIGILANCE IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS IN INDIA	S-61

EDITORIAL REPORT

Dr. Madhukar Akkala, M.Pharm., Ph.D,
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CRIHS-O-CEU-001

DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM RISEDRONATE

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ABSTRACT

The point of the present examination was to develop floating discharge formulation of Risedronate (RSD) Amongst the formulations prepared with Hypromellose K100M impeded the medication discharge as long as 12 "hours in the convergence of" 60 mg (RSD8). Present research work gastro retentive non effervescent floating matrix formulation of RSD Among all the formulations the formulations prepared by using HYPROMELLOSE K100M were unable to produce desired drug release, they were unable to retard drug release up to 12 hours. The formulations prepared with HYPROMELLOSE K100M retarded the drug release up to 12 "hours in the concentration of" 60 mg (RSD8). The formulations prepared with HYPROMELLOSE K4M were also retarded "the "drug release for more than" 12 hours". "Hence they were not considered".

KEYWORDS: RSD, Accural, Hypromellose.

How to cite this Abstract:

G. Ganesh, K. Priyanka, Reddy Sunil, A. Venkatesham. DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM RISEDRONATE. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-1.

CRIHS-O-CEU-002

BUPRENORPHINE-BUCCAL TABLETS

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ABSTRACT

*Mu*coadhesive buccal drug delivery systems offer many advantages over conventional systems such as ease of administration, rapid termination of therapy and administration to unconscious patient's. The aim "of the present study was to develop" buccal formulation of Buprenorphine "Polymers were used in the concentration of" 4 mg, 8 mg and 12 "mg concentration". Whereas from the dissolution studies it was evident that the formulation (BPN2) showed better and desired drug release pattern i.e., 98.06 % in 12 hours". The point of the present investigation was to create buccal discharge plan of Buprenorphine "to keep up consistent helpful levels" of the medication for more than 12 hrs. Different evaluations of normal were utilized as polymers. Buprenorphine portion was fixed as 8 mg. Every one of the plans were passed different physicochemical assessment parameters and they were observed to be inside cutoff points. Though from the disintegration ponders it was obvious that the detailing (BPN2) indicated better and wanted medication discharge" design i.e., 98.06 % in 12 hours.

KEYWORDS: Buprenorphine, Buccal Tablets.

How to cite this Abstract:

Gummuluri Sriram, E. Krishna Bhavani, Reddy Sunil, A. Venkatesham. BUPRENORPHINE-BUCCAL TABLETS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-2.

CRIHS-O-CEU-003

TAMOXIFEN CITRATE - ORAL DISPERSIBLE TABLETS

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ABSTRACT

*O*rodispersible tablets are not just shown for individuals who have gulping troubles, yet additionally are perfect for dynamic people. As of late orally deteriorating (OD) tablet innovation has been endorsed by United States Pharmacopeia (USP) and Centre for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER). In the present work, an attempt has been made to develop oral dispersible tablets of Tamoxifen citrate. Among all the formulations TXCT2 formulation showed maximum % drug release i.e., 98.79 % in 45 min containing Guar gum as super disintegrate in the concentration of 20 mg. In the present work, an attempt has been made to develop oral dispersible tablets of Tamoxifen citrate".

KEYWORDS: Tamoxifen citrate, Oral dispersible tablets.

How to cite this Abstract:

N. Naveen Reddy, MD. Iqbal Pasha, Reddy Sunil, A. Venkatesham. TAMOXIFEN CITRATE - ORAL DISPERSIBLE TABLETS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-3.

CRIHS-O-CEU-004

COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY OF “ROLL-ON” FORMULATION WITH VARYING METHODS OF DRUG LOADING IN TREATMENT OF ONYCHOMICOSIS

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ABSTRACT

The research focuses on change in performance of sertaconazole nitrate by varying the method of drug loading into a “Roll-on” formulation for the treatment of onychomycosis. “Roll-on” formulation which is a hydroalcoholic system with suitable polymer comprising less amount of organic solvent which offers various advantages over nail lacquer apart from improving residence time. Present study involves preparation of “Roll-on” formulations of sertaconazole nitrate by varying the method of drug loading such as plain drug, drug in surfactant and drug in microemulsions and evaluating comparative efficiency in terms of drying time, gloss, nonvolatile content, smoothness of flow, drug content and drug release. Roll on with microemulsions was found to be better system in performance as compared to other two.

KEYWORDS: Comparative Efficiency, Roll-On Formulation, Treatment of Onychomycosis.

How to cite this Abstract:

Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Purva Lad. COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY OF “ROLL-ON” FORMULATION WITH VARYING METHODS OF DRUG LOADING IN TREATMENT OF ONYCHOMICOSIS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-4.

CRIHS-O-CEU-005

FORMULATION AND IN-VITRO EVALUATION OF BILAYERED FLOATING TABLETS OF CANDESARTAN USING VARIOUS POLYMERS

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Email: shaikharunrasheed@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Candesartan is a non-peptide angiotensin II type-I (ATI) receptor antagonist which is used in the treatment of hypertension and congestive heart failure. Candesartan show extensive first pass metabolism and less bioavailability. Candesartan having low solubility and has half-life of 9 hrs suggests its suitability for an immediate release formulation. The basic study was aimed to identify a bilayered floating tablet of Candesartan with one immediate release and sustained release floating layer. The compatibility study of drug with excipients by FT-IR study reveals that there was no chemical interaction between the drug and excipients. Immediate release tablets were prepared by top spray granulation method by using sodium starch glycolate as superdisintegrant. Prepared tablets showed acceptable IPQC parameters and were evaluated for in-vitro drug release. Optimized batch (Batch F7) gave desired results in terms of % drug release after 15-30 min in pH=1.2, it gives <50% immediate release and gave results for sustained release tablets as 98 % in 8 hrs. Independent variables studied were, the drug : polymer ratio Sodium carboxy methylcellulose, Ethyl cellulose, Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose and gas generating agent(NaHCO₃). Drug release best fit model was both Zero order and First order. The mechanism of drug release was followed a non-fickian anomalous transport. Stability study of optimized batch was carried out at 45 ± 2 °C and 75 ± 5 % RH for one month and it was found that there was no statistically significant difference found in invitro drug release before and after stability study.

KEYWORDS: Angiotensin II type-I (ATI) receptor antagonist, Top spray granulation, Candesartan, Immediate release tablet, sodium starch glycolate.

How to cite this Abstract:

Shaik Harun Rasheed. FORMULATION AND IN-VITRO EVALUATION OF BILAYERED FLOATING TABLETS OF CANDESARTAN USING VARIOUS POLYMERS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-5.

CRIHS-O-CEU-006

ENHANCED INTESTINAL ABSORPTION AND BIOAVAILABILITY OF RALOXIFENE HYDROCHLORIDE VIA LYOPHILIZED SOLID LIPID NANOPARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

The current oral therapy with raloxifene hydrochloride (RXH) is less effective due to its poor bioavailability (only 2%). Henceforth, an attempt was made to investigate the utility of triglyceride (trimyristin, tri-palmitin and tristearin) based solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) for improved oral delivery of RXH. The SLN formulations prepared were evaluated for particle size, zeta potential and % entrapment and the opti-mized formulation was lyophilized. Solid state characterization studies unravel the transformation of RXH to amorphous or molecular state from the native crystalline form. Further the in situ perfusion studies carried out in rat intestine reveal the potential of SLN for enhanced permeation of raloxifene HCl across gastrointestinal barrier. To derive the conclusions, in vivo pharmacokinetic study was conducted in rats to assess the bioavailability of RXH from SLN formulation compared to drug suspension. Overall a twofold increase in bioavailability with SLN formulations confer their potential for improved oral delivery of RXH.

KEYWORDS: Raloxifene hydrochloride, SLN particles.

How to cite this Abstract:

Madhu Burra, Raju Jukanti , KN. Jayaveera. ENHANCED INTESTINAL ABSORPTION AND BIOAVAILABILITY OF RALOXIFENE HYDROCHLORIDE VIA LYOPHILIZED SOLID LIPID NANOPARTICLES. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-6.

CRIHS-O-CEU-007

DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MOUTH DISSOLVING TABLETS OF ZOLMITRIPTAN USING NOVEL SUPER DISINTEGRANTS

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ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out on Zolmitriptan Mouth dissolving tablets were prepared by direct compression method and different concentration super disintegrants like croscarmellose sodium, polyplasdone XL and Explotab were used in mouth dissolving tablets. A total of 9 formulations were prepared and evaluated for various pre and post compression parameters like angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, carr's index, hausner's ratio, weight variation, hardness, friability, thickness, wetting time, water absorption ratio, drug content, in vitro disintegration time, in vitro drug release. The in vitro disintegration time of the optimized formulation (F4) of Zolmitriptan was found to be 7 sec. Release rate of drug was 97.54% within 10 minutes. FTIR studies showed good compatibility between drug and excipients.

KEYWORDS: Zolmitriptan, Croscarmellose sodium, Polyplasdone XL, Explotab.

How to cite this Abstract:

MD. Yasmeen. DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MOUTH DISSOLVING TABLETS OF ZOLMITRIPTAN USING NOVEL SUPER DISINTEGRANTS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-7.

CRIHS-O-CEU-008

**DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MODIFIED RELEASE SOLID ORAL DOSAGE FORM
(ENTACAPONE)**

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ABSTRACT

The present research work focuses on design and development of modified Release solid oral dosage form entacapone: based on assessment of various parameters, in vitro drug dissolution profile and drug kinetics, hf14 was found to be optimized formulation. FT-IR & DSC studies revealed that there was no interaction between the drug and polymers used in the formulations. The drug release from f14 was found to fit zero order of concentration independent and best fitted to Higuchi model confirming to be diffusion assisted mechanism. Based on the mucoadhesive study, the optimized dosage form adhesive to gastro intestinal tract more than 12 hours. The marketed product released by first order kinetics by concentration dependent. In vivo bioavailability studies were conducted for optimized entacapone trilayer tablets and marketed product, the results were indicating that the optimized entacapone formulation was shown sustained release patterns where marketed product was shown immediate release.

KEYWORDS: Entacapone, Modified release, Mathematical modeling.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Sai Krishnam Raju. DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MODIFIED RELEASE SOLID ORAL DOSAGE FORM (ENTACAPONE). J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-8.

CRIHS-O-CEU-009

DESIGN AND CHARACTERISATION OF RIFAMIXIMIN MULTIPARTICULATE COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY

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ABSTRACT

Aim of present work was design and develop consistent and optimized formulations of Rifaximin multiparticulate targeted drug delivery to colon with the following objectives, explore multiparticulate CDDS to achieve localized effect and evaluate the pH- sensitive polymers such as Eudragit S 100 and L100 on Rifaximin, by reducing release of drug in pH conditions of upper GI tract while enhancing the release of formulations in alkaline surroundings of the colon. Also to optimize and evaluate in-vitro release and organ distribution of dosage forms in rat model, statistical assessment of polymer ratio's.

KEYWORDS: Rifaximin, Multi particulate DDS, Eudragit S100.

How to cite this Abstract:

G. Srujana. DESIGN AND CHARACTERISATION OF RIFAMIXIMIN MULTIPARTICULATE COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-9.

CRIHS-O-CEU-010

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ANTICANCER DRUG (TAMOXIFEN) LOADED NANOSPONGES**B. Raja Narender ***, **Dr. Rakesh K. Jat ¹**, **Dr. P. Raja Sridhar Rao ²**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research was to prepare Tamoxifen loaded Nanosponge gel for Sustained release of drug, increase the drug solubility, and increase the drug permeability, to reduce the dosing frequency and side effects. The FTIR studies proved that there were no interactions between the drug and Polymers. Homogenization technique followed by centrifugation was employed to prepare Nanosponge using various polymers. The formulation were prepared using different Polymers (hydroxy Ethyl cellulose and PVA) in different ratios (Drug: Polymer– 1:1, 1:1.5, 1:2, 1:2.5, 1:3, 1:3.5, 1:4 and 1:4.5) Using dichloromethane as cross linker as well as solvent. The formulations were characterized for drug entrapment efficiency. The Drug content of the formulations was observed to be from 62.90 to 95.94. The entrapment efficiency was found to be 68.97 to 99.44. The highest entrapment efficiency was observed with 98.68 and 99.44 for the formulations F4 and F8. The particle size analysis done by Malvern Zeta sizer showed that the average particle size of Tamoxifen loaded Nanosponge F3 average particle size of Tamoxifen loaded Nanosponge is 91.34nm and the poly dispersity index was found to be 0.196 and F8 average particle size of Tamoxifen Nanosponge F7 was 201.34nm and the poly dispersity index was found to be 0.178. The in-vitro release of Tamoxifen Nanosponge optimized formulation F4 was found to be 46.39 % and F8 was 45.56 % at the end of 24 hours. The drug content of the Gel G1 and G2 was found to be 84 % and 81 % respectively. The in-vitro release of Tamoxifen Nanosponge Gel formulation G1 was found to be 28.77% and G2 was 22.12 % at the end of 24 hours. The pH of the gels G1 and G2 was found to be 4.98 and 4.82 respectively. The Viscosity of the gels G1 and G2 was found to be 2.839×10^6 cps and 2.823×10^6 cps respectively. Both of the optimized formulations of the respected drugs followed first order release kinetics with hi-guchi mechanism. In-vivo test performed showed that the both the formulations of respected drugs able to retain the drug for prolonged periods of time to provide stable drug release and bioavailability

KEYWORDS: Tamoxifen, Nanosponge, Gel etc.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Raja Narender , Dr. Rakesh K. Jat, Dr. P. Raja Sridhar Rao. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ANTICANCER DRUG (TAMOXIFEN) LOADED NANOSPONGES. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-10.

CRIHS-O-CEU-011

FORMULATION AND IN VITRO EVALUATION OF FILMS FOR BUCCAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM
(OMEPRAZOLE)

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ABSTRACT

Now days, an extensive research is being carried out on the design and development of innovative drug delivery systems to improve the safety, efficacy and patient compliance. One such delivery system is the buccal film technology. This technology has emerged as an advanced alternative to the other conventional types of drug delivery systems. It is the proven technology for the systemic delivery of active pharmaceutical ingredients [API's]. The buccal mucosa is the best suited site for local, as well as systemic delivery of drugs due to its physiological features. The buccal film is an elegant and effective dosage form with improved bioavailability, when compared to other dosage forms as it bypasses the hepatic first pass metabolism. It is the most acceptable and palatable dosage form due to its small size, small dose and thickness of the film. Moreover, it does not require swallowing of the drug, which is most suitable for pediatric as well as geriatric patients. In the present study buccal films of itraconazole and omeprazole were developed and evaluated for various physicochemical properties, compatibility of the polymers used and stability of the prepared formulations the best formulation was selected depending upon the invitro dissolution data and stability studies. The drug release data was subjected to kinetic release mathematical models and observed that the both formulations followed zero order release kinetics.

KEYWORDS: Omeprazole, Films, Buccal route etc.

How to cite this Abstract:

T. Pandu Raju, Dr. Rakesh K. Jat, Dr. P. Raja Sridhar Rao. FORMULATION AND IN VITRO EVALUATION OF FILMS FOR BUCCAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM (OMEPRAZOLE). J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-11.

CRIHS-O-CEU-012

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL DOSAGE FORM EXHIBITING ANTI-ACNE ACTIVITYVanga Sridhar *¹, Pingili Mamatha² and S. Harikishan Prasad³^{*1} Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, ² Department of Pharmaceutical Biotechnology, INDIA.³ Department of Pharmaceutics, Vaageswari Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Karimnagar, Telangana, INDIA.Email: sreedher.vanga@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Acne vulgaris is a most common skin disorder of pilosebaceous unit that affect areas containing the largest oil glands, including the face, back, and trunk. It is generally characterized by comedones, papules, pustules, and nodules in a sebaceous distribution (face, upper chest, back). A comedone is a whitehead (closed comedone) or a blackhead (open comedone) without any clinical signs of inflammation. Papules and pustules are raised bumps with inflammation. The face may be the only involved skin surface, but the chest, back, and upper arms are often involved. *Propionibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* have been recognized as pus-forming bacteria triggering an inflammation in acne. *Staphylococcus aureus* support to cause inflammation in acne. The present research work deals with formulation and evaluation of herbal gels against this etiologic agent of acne vulgaris. The ethanolic and aqueous extracts of Banana Peel were prepared and formulated into a topical gel. In vitro antibacterial activity was performed against *P. acnes*, *S. epidermidis* and *S. aureus*, using agar well diffusion method. The measured zones of inhibitions of the prepared formulations were compared with standard antibiotic (Clindamycin). The prepared gels were evaluated for pH, viscosity, spreadability, stability, drug content, acute skin irritancy activity and in vitro diffusion. The results from the agar well diffusion showed that ethanolic and aqueous extracts of Banana Peel would inhibit the growth of *P. acnes*, *S. epidermidis* and *S. aureus* and the prepared herbal gels showed comparable antimicrobial activity against these bacterias with the marketed preparation. However, the standard Clindamycin was more active than that of prepared herbal gels, marketed herbal anti-acne preparation and extracts of Banana Peel. Taken together, our data indicated that ethanolic extract of Banana Peel had inhibitory and synergistic effect against *P. acnes*, *S. epidermidis* and *S. aureus*.

KEYWORDS: Anti-acne activity, *Acne vulgaris*, *Propionibacterium acnes*, Banana Peel, Herbal gel.**How to cite this Abstract:**

N. Naveen Reddy, MD. Iqbal Pasha, Reddy Sunil, A. Venkatesham. TAMOXIFEN CITRATE - ORAL DISPERSIBLE TABLETS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-12.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-001

POTENTIAL ANTI-PROLIFERATIVE AGENTS FROM 2,3-DIMETHYL BENZOCYCLOHEPTENONES-
PART 4

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*Benzosuberone nucleus containing natural products represents the medicinal and pharmaceutically important class of compounds because of their diverse range of biological activities. In former years, benzosuberone nucleus embedded with numerous natural products has been isolated. Benzosuberone unit has a core structure of natural products such as Colchicine, Theaflavin, Bussealin E, Demethylsalvicanol, Brussonol and Feveline which were clinically proven as anticancer agents. In view of our interest towards biologically active molecules²⁻¹¹ an efficient and eco-friendly method has been developed for the synthesis of 2,3-dimethylbenzocycloheptenone tethered thiadiazolo-pyrimidine carboxylates via a multicomponent condensation reaction of benzo[7]annulenyl thiadiazol-2-amines with various structurally divergent aromatic aldehydes and ethylacetoacetate in the presence of polyethylene glycol (PEG-400) and A valuable feature of this method was the design of new hybrid architectures through the adequate fusion of these subunits thiadiazoles or pyrimidines with benzosuberone, generating biological active leads. These synthesized compounds were evaluated against four human different cancer cell lines. Notably, compound **8k** showed prominent activity against all the cell lines. Moreover, efforts are also in progress to improve the antitumor activities of these potential leads, and other biological activity evaluation including antibacterial and antiviral activities are also underway in our laboratory.*

KEYWORDS: Anti-Proliferative Agents, 2,3-Dimethyl Benzocycloheptenones.

How to cite this Abstract:

Suresh Kasaboina, Uma Devi Holagunda, P. M. Gomedhika, S. Madhu, Lingaiah Nagarapu. POTENTIAL ANTI-PROLIFERATIVE AGENTS FROM 2,3-DIMETHYL BENZOCYCLOHEPTENONES-PART 4. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-13.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-002

STUDY ON ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY METHODS OF CITRUS SPECIES

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ABSTRACT

Waste materials such as peels of citrus species are rich sources of antioxidants. Now a days the recent area of interest includes exploiting the peels for the production of effectual, safe, inexpensive and novel nutraceuticals. The phenols and flavanoids present in citrus peel are responsible for antioxidant activity. The acetone extract of these peels exhibited greater potential to scavenge free radicals. These free radicals are produced during metabolic reactions and on accumulation they cause oxidative stress and damage cells, hence these chain reactions should be terminated. Hence to relieve this oxidative stress they can be used in preparation of nutraceuticals related to neurological disorders. The antioxidant activity of lemon peel was determined using DPPH assay, FRAP assay. The peels of Citrus linonum(lemon), Citrus aurantium(bitter orange), Citrus sinensus(sweet orange) ,Citrus limetta(sweet lemon) have good antioxidant property. Anti oxidants can be used in the formulation of nutraceuticals for skin, hair, heart and other nervous disorders. It even serves as potent antioxidant in food supplements.

KEYWORDS: Phenols, Flavanoids Nutraceuticals, Antioxidant, Citrus species.

How to cite this Abstract:

V. Lakshmi Aparna, Konda Ravi Kumar. STUDY ON ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY METHODS OF CITRUS SPECIES. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-14.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-003

STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF IVACAFTOR AND TEZACAFTOR IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

A new simple, accurate, precise and economical stability indicating RP-HPLC method was established along with sensitive stability indicating attributes for simultaneous estimation of ivacaftor and tezacaftor. Chromatographic separations were carried using Dionex, C18 (4.6 x 250mm, 5 μ m), column with a mobile phase composition of 0.1 M Na₂HPO₄ (60%) and methanol (40%) delivered at a flow rate of 1ml/min. The detection was carried out using waters HPLC auto sampler, separation module 2695 HPLC system with PDA detector at wavelength 232 nm. The retention time for ivacaftor and tezacaftor were 2.202 and 3.301 minute respectively. The correlation coefficient values in linearity were found to be 0.999 and concentration range 75-225 μ g/ml for ivacaftor and 50-150 μ g/ml for tezacaftor respectively. The percentage recoveries for ivacaftor were found to be 99.18 % and 100.18 % for tezacaftor. The proposed method was successfully applied for the simultaneous estimation of both the drugs in commercial combined dosage form.

KEYWORDS: Ivacaftor, Tezacaftor, RP-HPLC, Stability Indicating Validation.

How to cite this Abstract:

Anjali Bakshi, Laxmi Prasanna. M, Shweta Bhutada, M. Bhagavan Raju. STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF IVACAFTOR AND TEZACAFTOR IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-15.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-004

UV SPECTROSCOPIC ESTIMATION OF EZETIMIBE AND ROSUVASTATIN

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ABSTRACT

Rosuvastatin belongs to drug class of statins, used in combination with exercise, diet and weight-loss to treat high cholesterol and related conditions and to prevent cardiovascular disease. Ezetimibe is a drug that lowers plasma cholesterol levels. It may be used alone when other cholesterol lowering medications are not tolerated, or together with statins, when statins alone do not control cholesterol. A novel UV spectrophotometric method has been developed for the simultaneous estimation of ezetimibe and rosuvastatin in tablet formulation. Method is based on simultaneous equations method employing the wavelengths of maximum absorption of the drugs. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of 2-40 µg/mL for both the drugs with correlation coefficients (r^2) greater than 0.990. The developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines and the results were within acceptable limits for the parameters evaluated. The % assay for the drugs in the combined formulation was found to be in the range of 95% to 105% which were within acceptance limits. The developed method can thus serve as a powerful quality control tool for simultaneous determination of ezetimibe and rosuvastatin calcium in bulk and in combined tablet dosage form.

KEYWORDS: UV-Spectroscopic Estimation, Ezetimibe and Rosuvastatin.

How to cite this Abstract:

Celina Nazareth, Pratiksha Nagvenkar. UV SPECTROSCOPIC ESTIMATION OF EZETIMIBE AND ROSUVASTATIN . J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-16.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-005

DARIVATIZATION AND PHARMACOLOGICAL EVALUTION NEW 4-SUBSTITUTED 5-PHENYL-3-MERCAPTO 1,2,4-TRIAZOLE

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ABSTRACT

An efficient method for synthesis of 4 substituted 5 -phenyl - 3- mercapto -1, 2, 4 -triazole, by the mode of ring cleavage of oxadiazoles, nucleophiles are readily attack 5-phenyl 1,3,4- oxadiazole-2 – thiols and they are cleaved by acids and basis, in a reaction, which is the reverse of the ring closure, many nucleophilic ring cleavage reaction are followed by recyclization to give different heterocyclics, we were synthesized 5 different compounds and characterized its physical data, spectral analysis by IR and these compounds screened for possible CNS activity.

KEYWORDS: Mercapto, Triazoles, CNS Activity.

How to cite this Abstract:

Rasapelly Ramesh Kumar. DARIVATIZATION AND PHARMACOLOGICAL EVALUTION NEW 4-SUBSTITUTED 5-PHENYL-3-MERCAPTO 1,2,4-TRIAZOLE. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-17.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-006

A STABILITY INDICATING ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS QUANTIFICATION OF ARTEMETHER AND LUMEFANTRINE IN COMBINED DOSAGE FORMS BY RP-HPLCSwetha Sri R ^{1*}, Dr. Chaitanya M ², Madhavi A¹, Ramasubbaiah P ³, Rajani B ⁴

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ABSTRACT

A new high performance liquid chromatographic method was developed for the simultaneous determination of Artemether and Lumefantrine in pharmaceutical dosage form. Stability indicating studies have been performed under various stress conditions. The reported method adopts Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μ m, Make XTerra) column as stationary phase and a mobile phase consisting of Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer in the ratio of 80:20 (v/v) pH adjusted to 2.5 with ortho-phosphoric acid, employing UV detection at 274nm. Peaks eluted at a retention time of 2.003 min and 5.067 min was found to be Artemether and Lumefantrine respectively, where flow was monitored at a rate of 0.8mL/min. Linear calibration curves for proposed method are arrived in the concentration range of 25-125 μ g/ml for both the drugs ($r^2 > 0.999$). The method is validated in terms of precision, ruggedness, robustness and accuracy. The limit of quantification [s/n 10.05(ART) & 10.14(LUM)] shows the method meets the regulatory criteria. The proposed method successfully separated the drug from its degradation products when they were exposed to various stress conditions like photolytic, aqueous acid, base, thermal and peroxide conditions. High percentage of recovery shows that the method is free from the interference of excipients used in the formulation. Hence the method can be used in the routine quality control of these drugs.

KEYWORDS: Artemether (ART) and Lumefantrine (LUM), RP-HPLC, Validation, Degradation studies.

How to cite this Abstract:

Swetha Sri R, Dr. Chaitanya M, Madhavi A, Ramasubbaiah P, Rajani B. A STABILITY INDICATING ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS QUANTIFICATION OF ARTEMETHER AND LUMEFANTRINE IN COMBINED DOSAGE FORMS BY RP-HPLC. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-18.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-007

DESIGN, SYNTHESIS, ANTICANCER EVALUATION AND DOCKING STUDIES OF NOVEL PYRAZOLINE DERIVATIVES OBTAINED VIA REACTIONS INVOLVING CHALCONES

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ABSTRACT

1-(5-(4-substitutedphenyl)-3'-(4-fluoro-3-methylphenyl)-1'-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-1'H,2H-[3,4'-bipyrazol]-2-yl)-2-(quinolin-8-yloxy)ethanone derivatives were synthesised by treating the chalcones with hydrazine derivatives. The synthesized derivatives were confirmed by their IR, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C NMR and Mass spectral studies data. Cyclin dependent kinase 2 (CDK2), a major cell cycle protein, was identified as a potential molecular target of Pyrazoline derivatives. Furthermore, Pyrazoline derivatives have shown induced G1 cell cycle arrest, which is regulated by CDK2 in cancer cells. Therefore, we used molecular modelling to study in silico the possible inhibitory effect of CDK2 by the synthesized pyrazoline derivatives as a possible mechanism of these compounds as anticancer agents. The molecular docking study revealed that compounds possessing electron withdrawing groups such as Cl, F were the most effective compounds in inhibiting CDk2, and, this result was in agreement with cytotoxicity assay.

KEYWORDS: Design, Synthesis, Anticancer evaluation, Docking studies and Pyrazoline derivatives.

How to cite this Abstract:

Venugopal Muralidharan, S. Raja, Asha Deepti C. DESIGN, SYNTHESIS, ANTICANCER EVALUATION AND DOCKING STUDIES OF NOVEL PYRAZOLINE DERIVATIVES OBTAINED VIA REACTIONS INVOLVING CHALCONES. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-19.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-008

REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF PANTOPRAZOLE IN PURE AND ITS DOSAGE FORMS

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ABSTRACT

A rapid and precise reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed for the validated of Pantoprazole, in its pure form as well as in tablet dosage form. Chromatography was carried out on a Phenomenex Gemini C18 (4.6×250mm) 5 μ column using a mixture of Methanol: TEA Buffer pH 4.0 (70:30 v/v) as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0ml/min, the detection was carried out at 280nm. The retention time of the Pantoprazole was 2.302 \pm 0.02min respectively. The method produce linear responses in the concentration range of 10-50mg/ml of Pantoprazole. The method precision for the determination of assay was below 2.0%RSD. The method is useful in the quality control of bulk and pharmaceutical formulations.

KEYWORDS: Pantoprazole, RP-HPLC, Validation.

How to cite this Abstract:

S. Ushasree. REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF PANTOPRAZOLE IN PURE AND ITS DOSAGE FORMS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-20.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-009

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF LEVOFLOXACIN AND AMBROXOL HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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*Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.***ABSTRACT**

A new, precise, rapid, accurate RP-HPLC method was developed for the Simultaneous Estimation of Levofloxacin and Ambroxol HCl in pharmaceutical dosage forms. After optimization the good chromatographic separation was achieved by Isocratic mode with a Mixed phosphate buffer: ACN: methanol (40:40:20v/v%) pH4.5 as the mobile phase with Inertsil ODS C18-250X4.6mm, 5 μ , column as stationary phase at flow rate of 1 mL/min and detection wavelength of 223nm. The retention times for Levofloxacin and Ambroxol HCl found to be 2.737min and 4.793min respectively. The linearity of this method was found in the concentration range of 60 μ g/mL to 140 μ g/mL for Levofloxacin and 9-21 (μ g/mL) for Ambroxol HCl. The correlation coefficient R² value is found to be 0.997 for Levofloxacin and 0.995 for Ambroxol HCl. The LOD and LOQ for Levofloxacin were found to be 2.66 mcg μ g/mL and 15.69 μ g/mL respectively. The LOD and LOQ for Ambroxol HCl were found to be 8.05 μ g/mL and 47.55 μ g/mL respectively. This method was found to be good percentage recovery for Levofloxacin and Ambroxol HCl were found to be 101.28 and 99.32 respectively indicates that the proposed method is highly accurate. The specificity of the method shows good correlation between retention times of standard with the sample so, the method specifically determines the analyte in the sample without interference from excipients of tablet dosage form. The method was extensively validated according to ICH guidelines for Linearity, Range, Accuracy, Precision, specificity and Robustness.

KEYWORDS: UV spectrophotometer, Levofloxacin and Ambroxol HCl, HPLC.

How to cite this Abstract:

G. Sandhya. DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF LEVOFLOXACIN AND AMBROXOL HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-21.

CRIHS-O-CHEM-010

REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF RABEPRAZOLE IN PURE AND IT'S DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

A rapid and precise reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed for the validated of Rabeprazole, in its pure form as well as in tablet dosage form. Chromatography was carried out on a Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μ m) column using a mixture of Methanol and water (80:20 v/v) as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.8ml/min, the detection was carried out at 280nm. The retention time of the Rabeprazole was 2.379 \pm 0.02min respectively. The method produce linear responses in the concentration range of 20-100mg/ml of Rabeprazole. The method precision for the determination of assay was below 2.0%RSD. The method is useful in the quality control of bulk and pharmaceutical formulations.

KEYWORDS: Rabeprazole, RP-HPLC, Validation.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Raj Kumar. REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF RABEPRAZOLE IN PURE AND IT'S DOSAGE FORM. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-22.

CRIHS-O-COG-001

REVIEW ON HYPTIS SUAVEOLENS (L.) POIT (LAMIACEAE) - A POTENTIAL PLANT

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ABSTRACT

Plant kingdom is a treasure house of potential drugs and in the recent years, there has been an increasing awareness about the importance of medicinal plants. Drugs from plant sources are easily available, less expensive, safe, and efficient and rarely have side effects. Preliminary screening of phytoconstituents is a precious step in the identification and detection of bioactive principles present in medicinal plants and may lead to novel environmentally friendly bioherbicides and drug discovery. The plant *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit; [Lamiaceae] is reported to possess antifertility, anti-inflammatory and antiplasmodial properties. Traditionally, the plant extracts were used to cure swellings, abscesses haemorrhoid and also as memory aid. It has been used as a medicinal tea in many places in Asia and as a food and source of essential oil in South America. Plant Parts were used as analgesic and decongestant, and also to avoid fever and to fuel blood circulation with a sour, minty and sweet-smelling flavour. The English therapeutic journalisms show that it is efficient against bacteria and fungi but there has not been much research yet on its viral effectiveness. *Hyptis suaveolens* is an important source of essential oils, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, saponins, terpenes, and sterols, for example diterpenes: suaveolic acid, suaveolol, methyl suaveolate, two steroids: β -sitosterol, ursolic acid, two phenolic constituents: rosmarinic acid and methyl rosmarinate along with some other important constituents oleanoic acid, 3β -hydroxy lup-12-en-28-oic acid, urs-12-en-3 β -ol-27-oic acid, 1, 19 α -dihydroxy-urs-2(3),12-dien-28-oic acid and 3β -hydroxyl lup-20(29)-en-27-oic acid. For this reason and pursuant to the medicinal importance of the plant, this review is an effort to assemble all the information reported on its phyto-pharmacological activities, and information will lend a hand in generating attention towards the plant, and consequently, may be useful in emergent new remedies which may be more effectual and have better curative properties.

KEYWORDS: *Hyptis suaveolens*, Lamiaceae, Anti-Fertility, Anti-Inflammatory, Anti-Plasmodial, Anti-Spasmodic, Anti-Rheumatic and Anti-Soporific.

How to cite this Abstract:

Deepthi Yada, Dr. T. Siva Kumar. REVIEW ON HYPTIS SUAVEOLENS (L.) POIT (LAMIACEAE) - A POTENTIAL PLANT. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-23.

CRIHS-O-COG-002

PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF *TRIANTHEMA PORTULACASTRUM* LINN.

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ABSTRACT

Now a day, about 80% of the world population depends on traditional medicine for primary healthcare need. *Trianthema portulacastrum* Linn. (family: Aizoaceae) is a small perennial weed found in the Americas, Africa, India, and other regions of the world, is used extensively in Indian traditional medicines and also consumed as a vegetable throughout Asia for its perceived health benefits. Phytochemical investigation of *T. portulacastrum* (TP) reveals the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, and phenolic compounds. The principal constituents of TP are ecdysterone, trianthemine punarnavine, Beta-cyanin and 3,4-dimethoxy cinnamic acid. Emerging studies demonstrate that crude extracts as well as bioactive phytoconstituents of *T. portulacastrum* manifests potent antioxidant, anti-infective, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory activities. A growing number of in vitro and in vivo studies demonstrate various biological and pharmacological activities, including prevention and amelioration of hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, infectious diseases and cancer.

KEYWORDS: *Trianthema portulacastrum* Linn. Aizoaceae, Ecdysterone.

How to cite this Abstract:

Divya Yada, Dr. T. Siva Kumar. PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF *TRIANTHEMA PORTULACASTRUM* LINN.. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-24.

CRIHS-O-COG-003

TRIANTHEMA PORTULACASTRUM LINN. AND ITS UTILITY - A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Feverfew (*Tanacetum parthenium* L.) Now a day, about 80% of the world population depends on traditional medicine for primary healthcare need. *Trianthema portulacastrum* Linn. (family: Aizoaceae) is a small perennial weed found in the Americas, Africa, India, and other regions of the world, is used extensively in Indian traditional medicines and also consumed as a vegetable throughout Asia for its perceived health benefits. Phytochemical investigation of *T. portulacastrum* reveals the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, and phenolic compounds. Emerging studies demonstrate that crude extracts as well as bioactive phytoconstituents of *T. portulacastrum* manifests potent antioxidant, anti-infective, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory activities. A growing number of *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies demonstrate various biological and pharmacological activities, including prevention and amelioration of hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, infectious diseases and cancer. This review aims to present and analyze available literature to understand the potential of *T. portulacastrum* in health promotion and disease prevention.

KEYWORDS: *Trianthema portulacastrum* Linn. Aizoaceae, Anti-inflammatory, Hepatotoxicity, Nephrotoxicity and Abortifacient.

How to cite this Abstract:

Divya Yada, Dr. T. Siva Kumar, Dr. M. Sudhakar. TRIANTHEMA PORTULACASTRUM LINN. AND ITS UTILITY - A REVIEW. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-25.

CRIHS-O-COG-004

BIOTRANSFORMATION OF FRUIT LITTER IN TO VANILLIN BY FUNGI

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ABSTRACT

Vanillin is an important Flavouring agent. It is a plant secondary metabolite & a main constituent of natural Vanilla. In general vanillin is extracted from vanillin beans. Because of high cost of natural & synthetic vanillin, biotechnological pathway to produce vanillin has been proposed by many workers. Agrowaste containing Ferulic acid can be used to produce vanillin through microbial conversion. The present investigation was focused on the production of vanillin from Lignin, Ferulic acid & fruit litter of Albizzia lebbeck, Leucenea leucocephala, caesalpina pulcherima, using the white rot fungi Phanerochaete chrysosporium, which is a potent lignin degrader. The analysis was conducted using two different media: Saborauds & Minimal media. These media were supplemented with one of the substrates: Lignin, Ferulic acid, Fruit powders of Albizzia lebbeck, Leucenea leucocephala, caesalpina pulcherima at a concentration of 1%. Spectrophotometric analysis was performed for production of Vanillin with an interval of 24 hours for 7 days. Separate set of flasks were maintained for everyday analysis up to 7 days. Vanillin production by Phanerochaete chrysosporium was recorded for : Lignin, Ferulic acid, Fruit powders of Albizzia lebbeck, Leucenea leucocephala, caesalpina pulcherima and highest vanillin production was noted when Ferulic acid was used as the substrate in Saborauds (0.5mg/ml) & Minimal Media (0.675mg/ml) on 3rd & 2nd day of incubation. After Ferulic acid, Lignin had shown highest vanillin production in both the media. Out of the three fruits litter, maximum vanillin production was observed with Leucenea leucocephala in Saborauds media & Albizzia lebbeck in minimal media. caesalpina pulcherima fruit litter had also produced vanillin but less compared to others fruit litter.

KEYWORDS: Vanillin, Ferulic acid, Albizzia lebbeck, Leucenea leucocephala, caesalpina pulcherima, Phanerochaete chrysosporium.

How to cite this Abstract:

P. Mamatha, R.Ramakrishna, M. Shailaja Raj. BIOTRANSFORMATION OF FRUIT LITTER IN TO VANILLIN BY FUNGI. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-26.

CRIHS-O-COL-001

INVITRO ANTI-INFLAMMATORY SCREENING OF MARINE ALGAE SPECIES *SARGASSUM TENERRIMUM*

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ABSTRACT

The Studies on the bioactivities of marine algae have revealed numerous health-promoting effects, including anti-oxidative, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anti-cancer effects. The Sargassum tenerrimum were collected from different locations of Mandapam area, Tamilnadu The absorbance was measured using UV visible spectrophotometer at 255 nm. the percentage inhibition for chloroform extract are from 35±1.02 to 64±1.92, the percentage inhibition for methanol extract are from 45±1.12 to 72±1.42 and the percentage inhibition for standard diclofenac sodium are from 60±1.72 to 92±2.06 . The concentration are from 50, 100, 150, 200 µg/ml respectively. The percentage inhibition of inflammatory response is high in methanol extract when compare to chloroform extract.

KEYWORDS: Chloroform, Methanol, Diclofenac Sodium, Sargassum Tenerrimum.

How to cite this Abstract:

P. Pandian, K. Kathiresan. INVITRO ANTI-INFLAMMATORY SCREENING OF MARINE ALGAE SPECIES *SARGASSUM TENERRIMUM*. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-27.

CRIHS-O-COL-002

ESTIMATION OF PREVALANCE ON SELF MEDICATION AMONG PHARMACY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aims to provide the basic information on self medication practices among health sciences students in Hindu college of pharmacy which is affliated to Acharya nagarjuna university, A.P, India. It also estimates the prevalence of self medication in the study population.

Background: There is evidence that more and more people are taking greater responsibility for their own health, as witnessed by the self help movement of seventies and boom in herbal shows the little sign of abating.

Methods: A self-administrated questionarie based on google form was created and was send for more than 200 students for their email address, based on calculated sample size using raosoft sample size caluculator.

Results: Pharmacy students of different catagories were analysed that B.pharmacy students - 116 students there is 59.8% and Pharma .D students for 60 students 31% and M.pharmacy students for 18 students -9.2%

Conclusion: Self medication is prominent among the pharmacy students with 76% of respondents using some form of medications ,mostly pain killers and anti histamines .

KEYWORDS: Raosoft sample size caluculator, prevalence.

How to cite this Abstract:

Chandrika D. ESTIMATION OF PREVALANCE ON SELF MEDICATION AMONG PHARMACY STUDENTS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-28.

CRIHS-O-COL-003

SAFETY AND EFFICACY OF UNDENATURED TYPE II COLLAGEN IN THE TREATMENT OF OSTEOARTHRITIS OF THE KNEE

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aims to provide the basic information on osteoarthritis practices among people in a 100 bedded sanatorium by health sciences students of Hindu college of pharmacy, which is affiliated to Acharya nagarjuna university, A.P, India. It also estimates the safety and efficacy of undenatured type II collagen in the treatment of osteoarthritis of the knee in the treatment population.

Background: Arthritis afflicts approximately over 180 million Indians or approximately 15% of the India population. OA of the knee and hip is a growing health concern and is the most common forms of arthritis.

Methods: Briefly, at screening (Visit 1) the consent form was discussed, signed and a complete physical examination was performed. The VAS score, the WOMAC Index and Lequesne scores were obtained. A total of 52 subjects were recruited using the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The clinical assessments included WOMAC, Lequesne's functional index and 100-mm VAS pain scores.

Results: WOMAC score mean indicate significantly different, VAS score presents mean indicates significantly different from baseline. WOMAC score, treatment with UC-II reduced the WOMAC score by 33% as compared to 14% in glucosamine treated group after 90 days.

Conclusion: The efficacy of UC-II was studied in patients identified with moderate to severe OA. It was hypothesized that UC-II would reduce symptoms of OA of the knee to a greater extent than G.

KEYWORDS: Womac score, Osteo arthritis.

How to cite this Abstract:

Chandrika D. SAFETY AND EFFICACY OF UNDENATURED TYPE II COLLAGEN IN THE TREATMENT OF OSTEOARTHRITIS OF THE KNEE. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-29.

CRIHS-O-COL-004

RETROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DRUG UTILISATION OF PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS Vs H₂ RECEPTORS BLOCKERS

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ABSTRACT

Aim of Study: The objective of the study was to assess the retrospective observational comparative study on drug utilisation of Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPI) vs H₂ Receptor Blockers (H₂RB).

Methodology: 150 patients are included in the study. All the patients were undergoing proton pump inhibitors and H₂ receptor blockers therapy and /or co-morbidities were included in the study. The study was conducted in General Medicine Unit (IPD), Intensive Care Unit, Surgery, Orthopaedic and all other departments in a multi-speciality tertiary care hospital. The patient's demographic status like name, age, gender, occupation, IP number, date of admission, etc., were collected. The patient's lifestyle profile was collected by direct interaction with the patients or with their care takers for any lifestyle modifications. The appropriateness of proton pump inhibitors and H₂ receptor blockers drugs like dose, dosage form, duration of treatment, route and frequency of administration with standard guidelines was also recorded.

Result: Results of patient population included in the study are 150, out of males are 98(65%) and female are 52(35%) are using Anti-Ulcer drugs. Based on hospitalisation condition in total study population for fever and pain condition Pantoprazole (09%) given in 14 prescriptions and Ranitidine (11%) given in 16 prescriptions. In total study population based on dose and dose frequency Pantoprazole (PPI) 40mg, OD is prescribed in 17% of prescriptions and Ranitidine (H₂RB) 150mg, BD is prescribed in 14% of prescriptions. Based on use of Anti-Ulcer drugs in NSAID prophylaxis in total study population Pantoprazole is prescribed in 17% prescriptions and Ranitidine is prescribed in 13% prescriptions.

Conclusion: Gender, Age, Social habits, Occupation and Education status influence the occurrence of GIT problems. Based on this study, in our area, PPIs are prescribed more often than H₂RBs. In PPIs Pantoprazole (PPI) 40mg was the highest prescribed as prophylaxis to GIT damage than Ranitidine (H₂RB) 150mg.

KEYWORDS: Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPIs), H₂ Receptor Blockers (H₂RBs), NSAID Prophylaxis, Anti-Ulcer drugs.

How to cite this Abstract:

T.V.D. Vinoothna, G. Sadasiva Rao. RETROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DRUG UTILISATION OF PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS Vs H₂ RECEPTORS BLOCKERS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-30.

CRIHS-O-COL-005

EFFECTIVENESS OF VIRTUAL REALITY BASED THERAPY IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY – A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Cerebral palsy (CP) is the leading cause of childhood physical disabilities, affecting around 2 to 3 children per 1,000 live births. The symptoms of CP vary, but all individuals with CP have problems in motor function and are often accompanied by disturbances of sensation, perception, cognition and communication. Virtual reality (VR) is defined as the use of interactive simulations created with computer hardware and software to present users with opportunities to engage in environments that appear to be and feel similar to real world objects and events. VR has recently been explored as an intervention to improve motor function in children with CP.

AIM: In this review our aim is to analyze the effectiveness of virtual reality in children with CP, by studying various articles of evidence based research, meta analysis and case studies relating to virtual reality treatment in children with CP.

KEYWORDS: Virtual Reality (VR), Cerebral Palsy (CP), Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS), Meta Analysis, Cognition, Perception, Spatio-Temporal Gait, Psychomotor Function.

How to cite this Abstract:

Vedantham Satya Chakravarthy, Dr. Darabadi Rispa. EFFECTIVENESS OF VIRTUAL REALITY BASED THERAPY IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY – A REVIEW. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-31.

CRIHS-O-COL-006

THE EVOLUTION OF TREATMENT OF MAJOR DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS FROM PSYCHOSURGERY TO NEUROIMAGING AND NEUROMODULATION

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ABSTRACT

The treatment of psychiatric patients presents significantly clinical challenges to the clinical community and a multidisciplinary approach and a management is essential. In early stages when the psychopharmacology is in developing stage the psychosurgery has held as a fascination throughout the human history as an important method of influencing behaviour and consciousness. However, any discussion about psychosurgery invokes controversy as the widespread and indiscriminate use of transorbital lobotomy has led to several controversies and also responsible for several deaths of the mental illness patients. To overcome this effective psychopharmacological treatment eventually replaced the psychosurgeries, and accordingly the research and development of psychosurgeries is not forgotten. The recent resurgence of structural neuroimaging and neuromodulation has been evolved.

AIM: *The aim of this article is to provide a brief overview of the treatment for psychiatric disorders from psychosurgeries to neuroimaging and neuromodulation. It is important to encourage the development in the psychosurgeries and in the treatment of psychiatric disorder patients. Based on the considerations of historic and understanding the effect of the disease and pathophysiology of consciousness and behaviour and the adherence to research ethics.*

KEYWORDS: *Psychosurgery, Transorbital Lobotomy, Neuroimaging, Neuromodulation, Psychiatric Disorder.*

How to cite this Abstract:

Dasari Rama Krishna Prasad, Dr. Darabadi Rispa. THE EVOLUTION OF TREATMENT OF MAJOR DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS FROM PSYCHOSURGERY TO NEUROIMAGING AND NEUROMODULATION. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-32.

CRIHS-O-COL-007

THE EVOLUTION OF NEUROMODULATION SURGERY FOR PSYCHIATRIC DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT

As there is a several advances in the psychiatric treatment but some of the psychiatric disorders like schizophrenia, anxiety, depression, a significant number of patients become refractory and will not respond to specific treatment. Psychiatrists or clinicians are considering the neuromodulation surgery as the final step for these patients. Neurosurgical inventions aimed at treating the psychiatry patients are grouped into two categories. 1) Ablative psychosurgery, 2) neuromodulation psychosurgery. neuromodulation surgery involves implanting the device in the brain that changes the neuronal networks within the brain.

Aim: The major aim of this neuromodulation is to change the neuronal networks within the brain without damaging any other neurons. the primary goal of treatment of psychiatric disorders is to improve the functionality of the patients in the society. the development of these type of surgeries is not new in the psychiatric disorders but the change of the neuronal networks within, the brain is a special process which is recently developed by understanding the behavioural and consciousness of the psychiatric patients.

KEYWORDS: Neuromodulation, Psychiatric Disorders, Ablative Psychosurgery, Neuromodulating Psychosurgery, Neuronal Networks.

How to cite this Abstract:

Devarapu Neelima Chowdary, Dr. Darabadi Rispa. THE EVOLUTION OF NEUROMODULATION SURGERY FOR PSYCHIATRIC DISORDERS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-33.

CRIHS-O-COL-008

EVALUATION OF PATIENT ADHERENCE TO TB TREATMENT AND ROLE OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST IN IMPROVING PATIENT ADHERENCE

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ABSTRACT

Back ground: Tuberculosis is an infectious disease which is caused by Mycobacterium tuberculosis which mainly effects lungs and also other parts of the body. Patients with TB don't adhere to treatment and get serious effects by the disease. The objective of the study was to determine the patient adherence to tuberculosis treatment and role of clinical pharmacist in improving adherence to TB treatment.

Methodology: The single cohort prospective study was conducted on 115 TB patients and was carried out during November 2018 to April 2019 in Guntur city. The patient's demographic details were collected and also their adherence was checked using MARS (Medication Adherence Rating Scale). For every 2 months the patients were counselled about the importance of taking medicine and also about their life style modifications, diet. The patients follow up was done and noted into excel sheet and is calculated by using software called SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). In SPSS, descriptive analysis was used to plot the graphs and tables are analysed with chi square test.

Result: Results for the present study are, out of 115 patients 94(81.7%) are adherent and there are 21(18.2%) drop outs before patient counselling, after first patient counselling 91 (96.81%) are adherent and there are 3 (3.19%) drop outs, after second patient counselling 90 (98.90%) are adherent and there are 1 (1.10%) drop outs and after third patient counselling 89(98.80%) are adherent and there are 1 (1%) drop out. Finally, there are 26 (22.6%) drop outs and 89 adherent to tuberculosis treatment. And the main reasons for non-adherence before counselling are felt better and stopped medicine 5(19.2%),fear of side effects 5(19.2%), lack of counselling 7 (26.9%), fear of losing healthy relations 4 (15.3%), postponement for another day 1(3.8%) , moved away from dots centre 2 (7.6%).

Conclusion: Patients' adherence to TB treatment improved when a clinical pharmacist provided patient education on medication use and addressed patients' pharmaceutical care issues.

KEYWORDS: Tuberculosis, Adherence, Treatment, Counselling, Drop outs.

How to cite this Abstract:

U.N.S.V. Sugatri, G. Sadasiva Rao. EVALUATION OF PATIENT ADHERENCE TO TB TREATMENT AND ROLE OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST IN IMPROVING PATIENT ADHERENCE. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-34.

CRIHS-O-COL-009

ECONOMIC BURDEN AND REASONS FOR DELAY IN FIRST PSYCHIATRIC CONSULTATION - AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

It is estimated that in India about 25% population is suffering from severe mental illness and 10% have minor mental illnesses. In India, with its mix of rural and urban environment and cultural diversity, the proportion of the patients attending the psychiatric consultation, once the disorder is recognized is limited. Prevention of psychiatric disorders is complex due to its multifactorial etiology, such as genetic factors, life stressors, and neurochemical changes in the body. Though it is difficult to control all of these factors in order to prevent psychiatric disorders, the progression of the psychiatric illness can be interrupted by early identification and intervention. Early detection and intervention of the condition can shorten the duration of mental illness. Early treatment can also prevent complications and deterioration, i.e. severe disability, increased recurrence of episodic disorders, death due to suicide, and care giver burden. This study was conducted to detect the delay duration and various reasons for delay in first psychiatric consultation, in the patients attending the psychiatric out-patient department.

KEYWORDS: First Psychiatric Consultation, Economic Burden, Multifactorial Etiology, Diagnosis And Duration Of Delay, Traditional Healing.

How to cite this Abstract:

Dr. Darabadi Rispa, K. Bindu Madhuri, Dr. Shaik Faizan Ali, Dr. Syed Ahmad Basha. ECONOMIC BURDEN AND REASONS FOR DELAY IN FIRST PSYCHIATRIC CONSULTATION - AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-35.

CRIHS-O-COL-010

OUTCOMES OF LIVING RELATED KIDNEY TRANSPLANT RECIPIENT WITH TRIPLE IMMUNOSUPPRESSANTS (TACROLIMUS, MYCOPHENOLATE, STEROIDS) AT 6 MONTHS POST TRANSPLANTATION

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To determine the outcomes of living related kidney transplant recipient with triple immunosuppressants (tacrolimus, mycophenolate, steroids) at 6 months post Transplantation.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted in the department of Nephrology, KIMS, Hyderabad among living kidney transplant patients treated with triple immunosuppressive agents (tacrolimus, mycophenolate, steroids) at the end of 6 months.

Results: The whole study is on 30 patients out of which 30% patients were showing immediate graft functioning, 63.33% patients were slow graft functioning, 6.66% patients were delayed graft functioning at discharge. At the end of 6 months 30% of immediate patients are having an average of ≥ 86.73 GFR rates, 63.33% of slow patients are having an average of ≥ 52.98 GFR rates, 6.66% of delayed patients are having an average of ≥ 62.75 GFR rates.

Conclusion: Our data shows the GFR outcomes at the end of 6 months post transplantation of patients who had immediate, slow, delayed, graft functioning at discharge. The improvement and stability of graft functioning of recipients is illustrated.

KEYWORDS: CKD end-stage, GFR value, creatinine levels.

How to cite this Abstract:

T. Akhila, P. Keerthi, D. Kulkarni, Sreedharreddy. OUTCOMES OF LIVING RELATED KIDNEY TRANSPLANT RECIPIENT WITH TRIPLE IMMUNOSUPPRESSANTS (TACROLIMUS, MYCOPHENOLATE, STEROIDS) AT 6 MONTHS POST TRANSPLANTATION. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-36.

CRIHS-O-COL-011

SAFETY AND EFFICACY IN CURRENT MANAGEMENT OF TRACHOMA

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The study aims to provide basic information on trachoma practice among people in 300 bedded sanatorium by health science students of Hindu college of pharmacy, which is affiliated by Acharya Nagarjuna university, Andhra Pradesh, India. It also estimates the safety and efficacy of trachoma in population.

Background: Trachoma is a disease of poverty, overcrowding, and poor sanitation. Globally, about 80 million people have an active infection. In some areas, infections may be present in as many as 60–90% of children. Among adults, it more commonly affects women than men – likely due to their closer contact with children infection.

Methods: Review of literature. Measures to control trachoma are currently being stepped up in an effort to meet the WHO-supported target of global elimination of trachoma as a public health problem by the year 2020.

Results: Trachoma is one of the leading causes of preventable blindness in developing countries. It was reported as one of the seven most neglected tropical diseases that can be prevented via drug administration. Its infliction is primarily aimed at those living in areas deprived of clean water and proper sanitation. It is estimated that trachoma is the cause of visual impairment in about 2.2 million people worldwide of which about 1.2 million are completely blind. With implementation of the SAFE (surgery, antibiotics, facial cleanliness, and environmental control) strategy with support from the International Trachoma Initiative (ITI) the incidence of trachoma has decreased significantly in the Middle East and North Africa region.

Conclusion: With the enhancement of socioeconomic and sanitary status of people, advent of new generations of antibiotics, training of expert ophthalmologists and eye care facilities the prevalence of trachoma is decreasing.

KEYWORDS: Trachoma, Safety and Efficacy.

How to cite this Abstract:

P.V.S.N. Vimala. SAFETY AND EFFICACY IN CURRENT MANAGEMENT OF TRACHOMA. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-37.

CRIHS-O-COL-012

DECEASED DONOR KIDNEY TRANSPLANT WITH ATG INDUCTION AND TRIPLE IMMUNOSUPPRESSIVE AGENTS (TACROLIMUS, MMF, PREDNISOLONE)

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To determine the outcomes of deceased donor kidney transplant with ATG induction and triple immunosuppressive agents (tacrolimus, mmf, prednisolone).

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted in the department of Nephrology, KIMS, Hyderabad among kidney transplant patients treated with ATG induction and triple immunosuppressive agents (tacrolimus, mmf, prednisolone) at the end of 6 months.

Results: The whole study is on 30 patients out of which 16.66% (GFR value: ≥ 77.56) patients were showing immediate graft functioning, 60% (GFR value: ≥ 56.21) patients were slow graft functioning, 23.33% (GFR value: ≥ 31.5) patients were delayed graft functioning at discharge. Out of 30 patients cases, it is found that 3 patients were under infection episodes and no toxicity or drug induced effects of immunosuppressants and ATG induction.

Conclusion: Our data shows the GFR outcomes at the end of 6 months post transplantation of patients who had immediate, slow, delayed, graft functioning at discharge. The improvement and stability of graft functioning of recipients is illustrated.

KEYWORDS: CKD end-stage, GFR value, creatinine levels.

How to cite this Abstract:

P. Saipriya, K. Shobha, G. Sumalatha, Sreedharreddy. DECEASED DONOR KIDNEY TRANSPLANT WITH ATG INDUCTION AND TRIPLE IMMUNOSUPPRESSIVE AGENTS (TACROLIMUS, MMF, PREDNISOLONE). J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-38.

CRIHS-O-COL-013

COMPARISON OF DRUG THERAPY AND INTERVENTIONAL THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH UNCOMPLICATED HEART ATTACK

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aims to provide the best and effective therapy in heart attack among patients in a 300 bedded sanatorium by health science students of Hindu college of pharmacy, which is affiliated by Acharya Nagarjuna University, AP, India. It also estimates the efficacy of drug therapy and interventional therapy in improving quality of life and reducing treatment costs preventing complications like Persistent angina, Heart failure and death.

Background: CHD is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality throughout the world. It affects about 35 million people worldwide every year. Drugs like Anti-platelets, beta blockers, ACE inhibitors, statins, blood thinners are the renewed drugs for Heart attack. Interventional therapies include angioplasty and stenting, Percutaneous valve repair, balloon angioplasty.

Methods: Briefly at screening the consent form was discussed, signed and examination was done. Prospective randomised trails were made on 200 patients with MI from July 2018 to march 2019 with inclusion and exclusion criteria. The troponin levels in blood, Echo reports and ECG were obtained.

Results: The troponin levels of the patients were within normal range and 2D ECHO shows no abnormality in about 130 patients (65%) receiving drugs. In the OAT, it was reported that late presenting heart attack patients with blocked arteries had no better long term outcomes when they were treated with balloon angioplasty and stents than when treated with drugs alone. Avoiding stenting in stable late presenting patients could result in a yearly savings of nearly 60 million in health care costs.

Conclusion: Initial stent Implantation for heart attack showed no evidence of benefit when compared with medical (drug) therapy.

KEYWORDS: Myocardial infarction, Stents, Angioplasty.

How to cite this Abstract:

M.V.S.L. Priyanka. COMPARISON OF DRUG THERAPY AND INTERVENTIONAL THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH UNCOMPLICATED HEART ATTACK. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-39.

CRIHS-O-COL-014

PARACETAMOL SENSITIVITY AND TREATMENT APPROACH – A CASE REOPRT

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Paracetamol (acetaminophen) is a first line drug for fever. Ketoflam-P (flupiritine+Paracetamol) given as analgesic as the patient complained of fever and body pains. Ketoflam-P when taken along with regular Paracetamol (Acetaminophen) the patient developed urticaria and edema. Here we present the case of patient who came with fever and body pains and after taking these medications developed urticaria. She was treated with intravenous administration of anti-allergic/anti-histamines (pheniramine maleate) anti-ulcer (Ranitidine) anti-emetic (Ondansetron) Corticosteroid (Dexamethasone) along with withdrawal of Paracetamol and Ketoflam-P.

Case Presentation: This case report describes a 50yr old female patient with a diagnosis of fever, low BP (110/70mmHg) PR: 98Bpm. After taking the medications for a week she developed red colored rash/lesions all over the body. She was treated with anti-allergic, anti-ulcer, anti-emetic and electrolyte supplement through IV administration. And oral fexofenidine (anti-allergic) and Hydroxyzine (anti-histamine) along with topical Melipox spray. Her fever reduced but blood pressure decreased further (100/60mmHg). Only one case of urticaria has been described in the literature.

Conclusion: Clinician should have had considered the patient's sensitivity to paracetamol & LFT & Alcoholism. Ketoflam-P given in this condition might have triggered to the occurrence of urticaria & edema when taken along with regular Paracetamol consumption.

KEYWORDS: Paracetamol, Urticaria, Ketoflam-P, Hypersensitivity.

How to cite this Abstract:

K. Dulcie Moses, Dr. Shyam Sundar. PARACETAMOL SENSITIVITY AND TREATMENT APPROACH – A CASE REOPRT. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-40.

CRIHS-O-COL-015

ASSESSMENT OF APPROPRIATENESS OF ANTIBIOTIC PRESCRIPTIONS IN SURGICAL PROPHYLAXIS OF ORTHOPEDIC PROCEDURES

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To assess the appropriateness of antibiotic prescriptions in surgical prophylaxis of orthopedic procedures.

Methods: This was a prospective, observational study in which a total of 200 in patients subjected for surgical procedures in orthopedic department admitted in Srikara hospitals, Hyderabad were included. The study has begun with the approval of ethics committee.

Results: We assessed 200 orthopedic cases 28 % & 44% of Pre & Post OP are as per guidelines were as 72% & 56 & were not.

Conclusion: The current study revealed that there is inappropriate usage of antibiotics both preoperatively and post operatively. The most common mistake was selection of antibiotic which deviated from guidelines. Patient counseling regarding the antibiotic usage is also important.

KEYWORDS: Prophylaxis, Surgical site infection, Rational use, ASHP guidelines.

How to cite this Abstract:

Anju Sharma, T. Veena Priyanka Anand, Shubham Babu Gupta. ASSESSMENT OF APPROPRIATENESS OF ANTIBIOTIC PRESCRIPTIONS IN SURGICAL PROPHYLAXIS OF ORTHOPEDIC PROCEDURES. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-41.

CRIHS-O-COL-016

EVALUATION OF ANTIDEPRESSANT ACTIVITY OF HYPERICUM PERFORATUM USING EXPERIMENTAL MODELS OF DEPRESSION IN RATS

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ABSTRACT

Depression constitutes the second-most common chronic condition in clinical practice, exceeded only by hypertension. Despite recent progress achieved in the development of clinically relevant antidepressant drugs in recent years, the currently available antidepressant therapy is not at totally effective and it is associated with many undesirable collateral effects 32-35. In addition, only 60% of patients are responsive to the treatment with the available antidepressants. For this reason, the search for new drugs for the control of the symptoms associated with depressive disorders is still desirable. In the present study, 7 days pretreatment with CR at the doses of 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg showed antidepressant activity in the forced swim test and tail suspension tests. The FST is the tool most widely used for assessing antidepressant activity preclinically. The widespread use of this model is largely a result of its ease of use, reliability across laboratories, and ability to detect a broad spectrum of antidepressant agents⁴⁹. Most clinically active antidepressants are effective in the FST, while neuroleptics and anxiolytics produce different effects.³⁴ In the forced swim test, HP significantly reduced immobility period suggesting anti-depressant activity and the activity was comparable to the reference drug IMP. Immobility is a state of lowered mood or hopelessness, which the rats experience when they are allowed to swim in a restricted space from which they cannot escape.

KEYWORDS: Hypericum Perforatum (Hp), Antidepressant Activity.

How to cite this Abstract:

Dr. G. Chiranjeevi. EVALUATION OF ANTIDEPRESSANT ACTIVITY OF HYPERICUM PERFORATUM USING EXPERIMENTAL MODELS OF DEPRESSION IN RATS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-42.

CRIHS-O-COL-017

EVALUATION AND COMPARISON OF REGULATORY STRATEGY AND COMMUNICATIONS RECEIVED FROM VARIOUS REGULATORY AUTHORITIES DURING PRE & POST REGISTRATION OF “PIPERACILLIN AND TAZOBACTUM FOR INJECTION”

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ABSTRACT

Developing a new drug requires great amount of research work in chemistry, manufacturing, controls, preclinical science and clinical trials. Drug reviewers in regulatory agencies around the world bear the responsibility of evaluating whether the research data support the safety, effectiveness and quality control of a new drug product to serve the public health. Every country has its own regulatory authority, which is responsible to enforce the rules and regulations and issue the guidelines to regulate the marketing of the drugs. As the pharmaceutical industries throughout the world are moving ahead towards becoming more and more competitive, these are realizing that the real battle of survival lies in executing the work by understanding the guidelines related to various activities carried out to give an assurance that the process is under regulation. This article focuses on guidelines and regulatory requirements of different countries of different Regions like ASEAN, CIS, LATAM and African.

KEYWORDS: *Piperacillin and Tazobactum, Regulatory Strategy, Regulatory Authorities.*

How to cite this Abstract:

Dr. Hareesh Dara. EVALUATION AND COMPARISON OF REGULATORY STRATEGY AND COMMUNICATIONS RECEIVED FROM VARIOUS REGULATORY AUTHORITIES DURING PRE & POST REGISTRATION OF “PIPERACILLIN AND TAZOBACTUM FOR INJECTION”. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-43.

CRIHS-O-COL-018

INVESTIGATIONAL STUDIES ON CARCINOMA IN MALE RATS

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ABSTRACT

Purslane (Portulaca oleracea L., Portulacaceae) has been traditionally used in folk medicine to afford protection against liver injury, although its actual efficacy remains uncertain. Objective: To investigate the hepatoprotective and antioxidant effect of purslane seeds extract against hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) induced by Diethylnitrosamine (DEN). Materials and Methods: A total of 50 male Sprague-Dawley rats were randomly divided into five groups (10 rat/group) analyzed for a total experimental period 8 weeks. The first group was maintained as normal control, second group were treated with Purslane seeds extract (50 mg/kg of body weight) daily. Rats of remain groups were injected intraperitoneally with freshly dissolved in sterile 0.9% saline DENA (200 mg/kg body weight) and two weeks later, they received a subcutaneous injection of CCl₄ (3 ml/kg body weight/week) for 6 weeks. Rats of HCC + Purslane group were injected orally with Purslane seeds extract at a daily dose level of (50 mg/kg of body weight) two weeks after DENA injection while in Purslane + HCC group were injected orally with Purslane seeds extract before DENA injection. Serum and hepatic liver enzymes, blood reduced glutathione (GSH) and malondialdehyde (MDA) in red blood cells were determined and superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzyme also assayed. Caspases-3 was analyzed using flow cytometric analysis. Results: Serum liver enzymes, AFP, level of MDA and liver caspase 3 were increased in HCC group, while hepatic enzymes, tissue SOD and blood glutathione level were reduced. In groups treated with purslane seeds extract AFP, liver caspase 3, level of MDA and activity of liver enzymes were reduced and the activity of the antioxidant parameters were increased. Conclusions: Purslane seeds extract enhanced innate antioxidant activity and ameliorate the DENA-induced HCC and therefore can be used as a hepatoprotective drug in the future.

KEYWORDS: Purslane, antioxidant, hepatoprotective drugs, DENA, carbon tetrachloride, HCC.

How to cite this Abstract:

P. Aswini. INVESTIGATIONAL STUDIES ON CARCINOMA IN MALE RATS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-44.

CRIHS-O-COL-019

ACECLOFENAC-INDUCED PHYSICOCHEMICAL ALTERATIONS IN TOXICITY AMONG MALE ALBINO RATS

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ABSTRACT

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are associated with adverse renal effects caused by the reduction in synthesis of renal prostaglandins in sensitive persons or animal species, and potentially during long-term use in non-sensitive persons if resistance to side effects decreases with age. The effects of Aceclofenac sodium on the kidneys were studied during 4 1/2 hours in eight patients with normal renal function. Urinary output decreased within 10 min after the injection, and maximally by 80%. The renal plasma flow and the glomerular filtration rate initially diminished significantly, by 35%, but began to increase after only 2 hours. The dominant and persistent effect was a reduction of free water clearance, with maximum fall from 5.9 to 0.08ml/min after 2 1/2 hours. Aim: The aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of Aceclofenac-induced acute nephrotoxicity using biochemical parameters in rats. 12 male Wistar rats allotted in 4 equal groups were intraperitoneally injected with 0, 10, 50 and 100mg/kg Aceclofenac, respectively and 12 hours after injection, blood serum samples were collected for assessment of basic renal function test parameters such as urea, creatinine, and uric acid, sodium, Potassium. Rats treated up to 50mg/kg Aceclofenac were considered to be within normal range in rats. By increase in dose more than 50mg/kg showed significant increases in uremia were evidenced in intoxicated animals. Observed specifically in group IV Rats. In this study, uremia, as an indicator of kidney damage, was significantly increased depending on dose. Aceclofenac may cause kidney damage depending on dose and this effect may also be observed. NSAIDs-induced nephrotoxicity may be due to the inhibitory effect of these drugs on prostaglandin synthesis, thus causing kidney ischemia.

KEYWORDS: Aceclofenac, Impaired renal function, Nephrotoxicity, Uremia.

How to cite this Abstract:

P. Manju. ACECLOFENAC-INDUCED PHYSICOCHEMICAL ALTERATIONS IN TOXICITY AMONG MALE ALBINO RATS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-45.

CRIHS-O-COL-020

STUDY OF ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS ASSOCIATED WITH CHEMOTHERAPY OF BREAST CANCER

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The Aim of the present study is to assess the adverse drug reactions associated with chemotherapy of breast cancer, including evaluation of the relation between menopause status of patient and breast cancer, the relation between body mass index (BMI) and stage of breast cancer and the weight changes during chemotherapy of breast cancer.

Objective: The study is retro-prospective in design including all female patients admitted in day care ward for chemotherapy cycles. The main outcome observed was the presence of more perimenopause women (3040 years of age) with breast cancer.

Results: The percentage of common side effects were Nausea (75%), Alopecia (72%), Emesis (69%), Diarrhoea and Insomnia (64%), Asthenia (50%), Black nails (32%). There was a gradual reduction in weight of the study population

Conclusion: The study emphasized the need to focus on management of other side-effects, for close monitoring over side-effects, muscle strength, weight changes, psychological health of the patient and maintaining a separate data sheet or detailed written form for this purpose to help overall patient care. The study highlighted the enthusiasm among the study population regarding diet and diet pattern to be followed during chemotherapy of breast cancer.

How to cite this Abstract:

M. Mounika. STUDY OF ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS ASSOCIATED WITH CHEMOTHERAPY OF BREAST CANCER. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-46.

CRIHS-O-COL-021

DRUG UTILIZATION PATTERN OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE PATIENT UNDERGOING HAEMODIALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Aim: the Study is to analyze the drug utilization pattern in chronic kidney disease patients who was undergoing haemodialysis.

Method: The prospective study was done for a period of 6 months in Mallareddy Narayana hrudayala hospital in suraram. A total of 128 subjects were included in our study aged between 18 to 70 years above. Patient specific data was collected and assessed for drug prescription pattern.

Results: A total of 128 cases were made during study period, the overall drug utilization pattern of chronic kidney disease shows higher utilization of drugs were Hypertensive drugs(259 prescriptions, 88.29%) followed by anti-anemic drugs (209 prescriptions, 71.27%), vitamins and minerals (184 prescriptions, 62.76%), anti-ulcer drugs (94 prescriptions, 31.9%) were most frequently used.

Conclusion: In our present study we observed that the management of chronic kidney disease in nephrology department of Mallareddy Narayana hrudayala hospital, is with the rational utilization of medicines which is based on clinical knowledge, expertise and the guidelines accessible in the field of nephrology practice.

KEYWORDS: Chronic Kidney Disease, Drug Utilization Pattern, Haemodialysis.

How to cite this Abstract:

Y. Sreehari Bharadwaj, Dr. Rajkamal, Dr. Shubham babu Gupta M. DRUG UTILIZATION PATTERN OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE PATIENT UNDERGOING HAEMODIALYSIS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-47.

CRIHS-O-COL-022

ROLE OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST TO IMPROVE THE ADHERENCE OF CONTRACEPTION

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ABSTRACT

Background: Although contraceptive methods are an essential elements of contraception for the management of unintended pregnancies, adherence is often suboptimal to them. Pharmacists are increasingly being integrated into primary care as a part of the move towards a patient centered medical home and may have a positive influence on contraceptive use. We examined whether the presence of pharmacists in primary care clinics was associated with higher contraceptive adherence.

Methods: It is an prospective study which was undertaken on a sample size of 125 subjects over a period of 6months. Subjects of an age group 18 and above were considered based on the inclusion criteria. They were provided with patient counseling about the methods, their usage, risks and benefits associated with them.

Results: Sixty three (63) subjects were counseled during the study period. Majority of the counseled subjects were of age group 24(50%). Minimum time taken to counsel the subject was 6-10minutes. Mean counseling time for educated subjects was 7.5minutes and for uneducated it was 11.43minutes. Subject was provided counseling on;

- Selection of method?
- Benefits and risks of the method?
- Managing the risks associated by the method?

We found significant association between pharmacist presence and clinic level contraceptive adherence. However adherence was lower in subjects without patient counseling.

Conclusion: Pharmacist presence regardless of any barriers was associated with improved contraceptive adherence in primary care clinic. The subjects not only understood the use of the method but also improved their therapeutic outcomes. This can be further enhanced by encouraging pharmacist to enroll in continuous education activities that provide updated information about contraceptive methods.

KEYWORDS: Contraception, Adherence, Patient counseling.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Kiranmai, Dr. Sadanandam. ROLE OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST TO IMPROVE THE ADHERENCE OF CONTRACEPTION. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-48.

CRIHS-O-COL-023

CANCER THERAPY-RELATED CARDIAC DYSFUNCTION AND HEART FAILURE

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ABSTRACT

Advances in cancer therapy have resulted in significant improvement in long-term survival for many types of cancer, but have also resulted in untoward side effects associated with treatment. One such complication is the development of Cardiomyopathy and heart failure, so the team of oncologists and cardiologists must be better equipped with an evidence-based approach to care for these patients across the spectrum. Prevention and treatment aspects have been discussed, concluding with the section on evidence gap and future directions. Risk of toxicity was increased in patients with advanced age, multiple co-morbidities and in those with prolonged treatment.

KEYWORDS: Heart failure, Cancer therapy, Cardiotoxicity, LVEF.

How to cite this Abstract:

K. Maneesha. CANCER THERAPY-RELATED CARDIAC DYSFUNCTION AND HEART FAILURE. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-49.

CRIHS-O-COL-024

BREAST CANCER: THERAPEUTIC APPROACHES AND CHARACTERISTIC OBSERVATIONAL STUDY IN PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Breast cancer remains the highest prevalent cancer amongst women worldwide. The risk of breast cancer has been coupled to the prevalence of obesity over the last decade as a result of the hormonal and health complexities connected to it. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy has proved appealing potential benefits over the classic adjuvant therapy. The aim of this work is to study the cancer characteristics, incidence of obesity, and to understand the therapeutic implications in breast cancer. The study was carried out in a tertiary care hospital located in Hyderabad, India. The sample size concurring to be 173 Case studies. 46 patients were analyzed on the state of depression based on a PHQ-9 questionnaire. The obtained results gave p-value of 0.004 which is < 0.05 showing that obesity is a significant factor in breast cancer patients. One-way ANOVA was performed on the data for the tumor size outcomes and the p value was found to be 0.0001 (P-value <0.05) which suggests that there is a significant difference in tumor size after 4 cycles of Doxorubicin. The state of depression was analyzed among 46 patients using PHQ-9 questionnaire. The analyzed scores showed that 17.4% of the patients were at Minimal depression state, 43.5% were having Mild depression thoughts, 21.7% were having Moderate depression and 15.2% and 2.2% of the population were suffering from Moderately Severe and Severe depression respectively. The study shows a significant prevalence of obesity in breast cancer patients amongst the considered population. Being overweight or obese can lead to increase in significant risk of acquiring carcinoma. The use Doxorubicin for neoadjuvant therapy was found to be significantly beneficial in the reduction of tumor size of locally advanced breast cancers (LABC).

How to cite this Abstract:

M. Pavan. BREAST CANCER: THERAPEUTIC APPROACHES AND CHARACTERISTIC OBSERVATIONAL STUDY IN PATIENTS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-50.

CRIHS-O-COL-025

EVALUATION OF RATIONAL USE OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR SURGICAL PROPHYLAXIS

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To evaluate the rational use of antibiotics as surgical prophylaxis and assess the patient knowledge regarding the usage of antibiotics.

Methods: This was a prospective, observational study in which a total of 250 in patients subjected for surgical procedures in gynecology and obstetrics, orthopedics and general surgery admitted in Malla reddy Narayana hospital, Hyderabad were included. The study has begun the approval of ethics committee.

Results: We assessed 250 cases of which 75 gynecology and obstetrics surgical cases of which 33.3% & 36% of Pre & Post-operative antibiotics were according to guidelines and 66.6% & 64 % were deviated, Out of 75 orthopedic cases 28 % & 44% of Pre & Post OP are as per guidelines were as 72% & 56 & were not. 100 General surgery cases were assessed & found to be Pre & Post- OP cases 58% & 82% were as per guidelines where as 34% of Pre & 17% of Post OP deviated from guidelines.

Conclusion: The current study revealed that there is inappropriate usage of antibiotics both preoperatively and post operatively. The most common mistake was selection of antibiotic which deviated from guidelines. Patient counseling regarding the antibiotic usage is also important.

KEYWORDS: Prophylaxis, Surgical site infection, rational use, ASHP guidelines.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Prashanth Naidu. EVALUATION OF RATIONAL USE OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR SURGICAL PROPHYLAXIS. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-51.

CRIHS-O-COL-026

OBSERVATIONAL STUDY TO MEASURE ANTI-EPILEPTIC DRUG ADHERENCE

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ABSTRACT

Aim: A study to measure Anti- Epileptic drug Adherence and also to identify factors affecting the drug adherence among people with epilepsy

Method: A total number of 100 patients affected with epilepsy that fulfilled the inclusion criteria were recruited in the study. In this study purposive sampling technique was used. The total period of the study was from September 2018- April 2019. A validated self-prepared questionnaire was used to assess the drug adherence level among people with epilepsy.

Results: Majority of then Patients used Valproic Acid (32%) drug for treatment 71% of prescription has Poly therapy for treating epilepsy sample are compliant to the medication. 73 (73%) patients never missed their dose and are compliant to the AEDs. 10 (35%) patients had uncategorized reasons for non-adherence. 44 (44%) patients experienced side effects, in that majority [41%] of sample experienced drowsiness. 27 (61%) patients are not affected by the side effects. The study shows a significant relationship between history of non- adherence and current status of non-adherence [P-value 7.879 > 0.05 level of confidence].

Conclusion: There was no significant relationship between drug non-adherence and age, education, residence, duration of illness, side effects, expenditure of medicine. There was a significant relationship between history of non-adherence and current status of non- adherence.

KEYWORDS: Epilepsy, Drug- Adherence, Non- adherence.

How to cite this Abstract:

V. Sumanth Roy, Dr. Rajkamal, Dr. Shubham Babu Gupta. OBSERVATIONAL STUDY TO MEASURE ANTI-EPILEPTIC DRUG ADHERENCE. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-52.

CRIHS-O-COL-027

A STUDY OF MEDICATION ERRORS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To evaluate the occurrence of medication errors in tertiary care hospitals

Objectives: A prospective and observational study was conducted in general medicine and orthopaedic ward of Malla Reddy Narayana Hrudayala Hospital, Hyderabad during August -2018 to January-2019. Medication errors were categorized as prescription error, dispensing error, administration error. The case records and treatment charts were reviewed.

Results: A total of 300 patients (150 in general medicine and 150 in orthopaedic ward) were included during the study period. Total number of MEs was 108(36%) of which, 56(38%) were in general medicine and 52(35%) were in orthopaedic wards. The most common MEs was PEs 70(65%) followed by AEs 33(31%).

Conclusion: There is a need to establish ME reporting system to reduce its incidence and improve patient care and safety.

How to cite this Abstract:

V. Shivani. A STUDY OF MEDICATION ERRORS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-53.

CRIHS-O-COL-028

CASE STUDY ON LYME DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

Case History: A 42 years old female patient was admitted in medical wing with c/o fever with intermittent shivering, Flu, Headache, Generalized joint pains, Excess thirst fluid intake progressive rash on her back associated with itching, Burning.

History Of patient noticed initial small raised lesion resembling an insect bite, Fever reached 102.8F with increased burning sensation, Bump developed into a circular rash.

On Examination: Large circular rash on her back 16*18 diameter. A provisional diagnosis of Dermatitis further confirmation is done by investing lab data. After going through all investigations and based on symptoms the patient is diagnosed as Lyme disease. The prognosis is good and a follow up is recommended for every 1 week till the drug regimen is complete.

KEYWORDS: Dermatitis, flu, Lyme Disease.

How to cite this Abstract:

Sowjanya I, Dr. Pabba Parameshwar. CASE STUDY ON LYME DISEASE. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-54.

CRIHS-O-COL-029

ADVANCES IN GENE THERAPY AND THE ROLE OF PHARMACIST IN GENE THERAPY

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ABSTRACT

Recent scientific and clinical break through in gene therapy offer hope to patients who live with cancer, retinal, hemophilia and neurological conditions and other diseases. Gene therapy is the introduction, removal (or) change in the content of persons genetic code with a goal of treating or curing a disease. Now a days pharmacist are also involved in gene therapies and updating the knowledge on these products for QOL of the patient.

KEYWORDS: *Gene therapy, Gene transfer, Role of Pharmacist.*

How to cite this Abstract:

V. Ushasree. ADVANCES IN GENE THERAPY AND THE ROLE OF PHARMACIST IN GENE THERAPY. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-55.

CRIHS-O-COL-030

IMPACT OF PATIENT COUNSELLING ON HTN

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The aim is to evaluate the effect of patient counseling in major risk factors based on readmissions and emergency department revisits and patient medication compliance as outcome of the study, to analyse the communication between pharmacist and patients about lifestyle changes in hypertension care, to evaluate the effects of pharmaceutical interventions.

Methods: A prospective observation study was carried out in department of cardiac wing at malla reddy hospital, data was collected from 300 patients and it was proposed to be conducted for 1 year.

Results: Out of 300 patient's 150 patients were in control group and 150 patients were in intervention group. Among 150 patients who were in intervention, 100 patients came with positive outcome among those 60(60%) were male and 40(40%) were female, 20 patients didn't follow among those 12(60%) were male and 8(40%) were female and remaining 30 patient came with negative outcome among those 19(63.6%) weremale and 11(36.4%) were female.

Conclusion: The patient counselling program resulted in better control of blood pressure and reduced cardiovascular risk scores in hypertension patient.

How to cite this Abstract:

Anusha Patil, DR. Raj Kamal. Dr. Sechana. IMPACT OF PATIENT COUNSELLING ON HTN. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-56.

CRIHS-O-COL-031

CASE PRESENTATION ON CONGENITAL ACYANOTIC HEART DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To Present The Case study on Congenital Acyanotic Heart Disease.

Method: SOAP Analysis.

Source: Cardiac Wing, Mallareddy Narayana Hrudayalaya Multispeciality Hospital, Suraram.

Main Body: Explaining about the Disease, Epidemiology, Etiology, Pathophysiology, Clinical presentation, Diagnosis, Therapy with the example of Case presentation on Congenital Acyanotic Heart Disease.

Conclusion: There is a need for further Research and Treatment implications for the Disease and There is need for framing policies and Guidelines to be done.

How to cite this Abstract:

Ch. Raju, Dr. Rajkamal, Dr.Shubham Babugupta, Dr.Sadanandam. CASE PRESENTATION ON CONGENITAL ACYANOTIC HEART DISEASE. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-57.

CRIHS-O-COL-032

PHARMACOEPIDEMIOLOGICAL STUDY ON CEREBROVASCULAR

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The aim is to conduct pharmacoepidemiology study on Cerebrovascular Accident patient by evaluating the use and the effects of drugs and quantification of adverse drug reactions, drug utilisation studies to improve the quality and use of medicine, designing interventions to improve prescribing pattern of drug.

Methods: A prospective observation study was conducted in department of general medicine and ICU at mallareddy hospital, data was collected from 130 patients and it was proposed to be conducted for 6 months.

Results: Among 130 patient's 78 (60%) are males and 52 (40%) are females. Among all the age groups major number of CVA patients were seen in 60-69 years (30%). In females ischemic stroke (88.46%), hemorrhagic stroke (11.53%) and in males ischemic stroke (94.87%), hemorrhagic stroke (5.12%) Among them 92% of stroke are ischemic majorly seen in both male's and female's. Ischemic stroke (94.87%) is majorly seen in 60-69 years age group. Hypertension (36.43%) is a major risk factor found in males (60%) and females (40%). Among hyperlipidemia (26.72%), diabetes mellitus (16.19%) and alcohol consumption (20.64%). Antiplatelet drug's (25.75%) are the highest number of drugs given in patients 71.27% in males and 28.72% in females. Next to this lipid lowering drugs (24.38%) are given mostly. Highest number of drugs are given in 50-59 years age group and are antiplatelet drug's. As a clinical pharmacist 16 ADRS and 25 drug interactions are reported and treated and follow up is taken to know the medication adherence and relapse.

Conclusion: proper patient counselling is needed to reduce hypertension and to reduce the risk for CVA. Among all the drugs antiplatelet drug's are majorly given in males and lipid lowering drugs in females.

KEYWORDS: Hypertension (HTN), Cerebrovascular Accident (CVA).

How to cite this Abstract:

MD. Mansoor Ali, Dr. Sadanandam. PHARMACOEPIDEMIOLOGICAL STUDY ON CEREBROVASCULAR. J Pharm Res 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-58.

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ASSESSMENT OF SENSORIMOTOR DYSFUNCTION OF THE WRIST: A SCOPING REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Injuries to the wrist joint can affect proprioception and overall function of the upper limb. Assessment of wrist proprioception requires the need for reliable and valid tests. To our knowledge no previous studies have reported the psychometric properties of tests to identify sensorimotor dysfunction of the wrist joint. Hence the objective of this review to comprehensively provide an overview of the tests that assess proprioceptive function of the wrist.

Methodology: We followed the Prisma extension for reporting of scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR). A systematic literature search of databases Pub med, Scopus, CINAHL, Web of science and Cochrane electronic databases will be conducted from inception to September 2019. Two reviewers will independently screen the studies for titles, abstracts and full texts of the relevant articles will be retrieved. A narrative synthesis of the findings will be presented.

KEYWORDS: Wrist, Proprioception, Sensory Motor, Joint Positioning Sense, Active Reposition Error, Passive Reposition Error, Psychometric Properties, Outcome Measures, Reliability, Validity.

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A STUDY AND REVIEW OF TOPICAL CORTICOSTEROID ABUSE IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Topical corticosteroids (TC) are the most common and widely abused drug in India. They provide rapid symptomatic relief, especially in a short duration. After prolonged TC use, severe rebound erythema, burning and scaling on the body were seen, if attempted cessation. Despite being the most useful drug, they are known to produce severe local, systemic and psychological side-effects when overused or misused.

Aim: To study the demographics, magnitude and clinical features of TC misuse to raise awareness. To analyse its causes and to know the extent of abuse of these drugs. To find out the source of these drugs which will help to know about the harmful effects.

Material and Methods: This is a prospective study done in Kurnool Medical College, Kurnool. Data were collected from September 2018 till August 2019 from Department of Dermatology in Kurnool medical college.

Results: In our Annual study on TC abuse, it was observed that out of 7,200 OPD patients, 80 patients were detected with TC induced complications. Out of 80 patients, 50(62.5%) were females & 30 (37.5%) were males. The prevalence of these cases was 1.11%. Out of the cases diagnosed, the most common ones were: steroid-induced Acne, Melasma, Striae and Tinea Incognito.

Conclusion: A Strict implementation of the existing regulations is needed to prevent their widespread abuse. Indian drug regulatory agency has to take proactive steps to ensure the availability of only approved TC in the country. It is imperative to give awareness to people about the possible complications of these TC and the extent of the problem the society is facing because of irrational and unregulated use of these drugs.

KEYWORDS: Topical corticosteroids, Abuse, Awareness.

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CRIHS-O-MED-002

AN OVERVIEW AND ASSESSMENT OF MATERIOVIGILANCE IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Materiovigilance envisages close monitoring of any undesirable performance of a medical device by identifying, collecting, reporting with an estimate of adverse events and reacting to them with field safety corrective actions or device recall during the post-marketing phase of a Medical Device¹. This study highlights the importance of materiovigilance programme of India and the need to report Medical Device Adverse Events (MDAE).

Aim and Objective: The study aims to assess the knowledge of Materiovigilance among healthcare professionals working in tertiary care hospitals in India.

Materials & Methods: A Questionnaire-based cross-sectional study among doctors, nursing staff and technicians, was done. Data collected through online forms was assessed using Microsoft Excel (ver.2010). Descriptive data are presented in percentages, and a chi-square test was used to test the significance.

Results: About 60.73% knew the purpose of materiovigilance. Only 47.8% knew the existence of MvPI and 22.08 % (36) had seen the MDAE form. Eight respondents admitted that they had reported MDAE. About 7.36% (12) agreed that they were trained to report medical device adverse events.

Conclusion: Inadequate practice was observed, in spite of having adequate knowledge of materiovigilance. There is a need to train healthcare professionals on materiovigilance, impressing upon them the need for early detection & prevention of Medical Device Adverse Events.

KEYWORDS: Materiovigilance, Medical Device Adverse Event (MDAE), Assessment, Healthcare Professionals.

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